

TO THE QUESTION OF THE CATEGORY "HERO" IN A WORK OF
ART

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Annotation. The article explores the category of "hero" in the theory of literature. The concepts of a literary hero, character, character, type, artistic image, etc. are considered, and the distinctive features of these categories are revealed.

Key words: hero, image, character, narrator, plot, type, artistic narrator.

In literary works, images of people are invariably present and, as a rule, fall into the focus of readers' attention, and in some cases, their likenesses: humanized animals, plants ("Attalea princeps" by V.M. Garshin) and things (fairytale hut on chicken legs). There are different forms of human presence in literary works. This is a narrator-narrator, a lyrical hero and a character capable of revealing a person with the utmost fullness and breadth. This term is taken from French and is of Latin origin. The ancient Romans used the word "persona" to designate a mask worn by an actor, and later a face depicted in a work of art [1, P.25].

As synonymous with this term, there are now the phrases "literary hero" and "character". However, these expressions also carry additional meanings: the word "hero" emphasizes the positive role, brightness, unusualness, exclusivity of the depicted person, and the phrase "actor" emphasizes the fact that the character manifests himself mainly in performing actions [1, P.32].

A character is either the product of the writer's pure fiction (Gulliver and the Lilliputians in J. Swift; Major Kovalev who lost his nose in N.V. Gogol) or the result of inventing the appearance of a real person (whether historical figures or people

biographically close to the writer, or even himself); or, finally, the result of the processing and completion of already known literary heroes, such as, say, Don Juan or Faust. Along with literary heroes as human individuals, sometimes group, collective characters turn out to be very significant (the crowd on the square in several scenes of "Boris Godunov" by A. S. Pushkin, testifying to the opinion of the people and expressing it).

The character has a dual nature. He, firstly, is the subject of the depicted action, the stimulus for the unfolding of events that make up the plot. It was from this side that V. Ya. Propp in his world-famous work *Morphology of a Fairy Tale* (1928). The scientist spoke about fairy-tale heroes as carriers of certain functions in the plot and emphasized that the faces depicted in fairy tales are significant primarily as factors in the movement of event series. A character as a character is often denoted by the term actant (lat. acting). Secondly, and this is almost the main thing, the character has an independent significance in the composition of the work, independent of the plot (event series): he acts as a carrier of stable and stable (sometimes, however, undergoing changes) properties, traits, qualities.

Characters are characterized by the actions they perform (almost in the first place), as well as forms of behavior and communication (because not only what a person does is significant, but also how he behaves at the same time), features of appearance and close circle (in particular, things belonging to the hero), thoughts, feelings, intentions. And all these manifestations of a person in a literary work (as well as in real life) have a certain resultant – a kind of center, which M.M. Bakhtin called the core of personality, A.A. Ukhtomsky – the dominant, determined by the starting intuitions of a person. To designate a stable core of consciousness and behavior of people, the phrase value orientation is widely used [4, P. 119-127].

Type – a generalized artistic image, the most possible, characteristic of a particular social environment. A type is a character that contains a social generalization. For example, the type of “superfluous person” in Russian literature, with all its diversity (Chatsky, Onegin, Pechorin, Oblomov), had common features: education, dissatisfaction with real life, the desire for justice, the inability to realize

oneself in society, the ability to have strong feelings, etc. e. Each time gives birth to its own types of heroes. The “extra person” was replaced by the type of “new people”. This, for example, is the nihilist Bazarov.

Literary type (hero type) – a set of characters who are close in their social status or occupation, worldview and spiritual appearance. Such characters can be represented in various works by the same or several writers.

Literary types are a reflection of the tendencies of the spiritual development of society, worldview, philosophical, moral and aesthetic views of the writers themselves. The spread of this or that literary type can be dictated by the "social order", that is, the need of society, readers to depict people with some kind of stable set of qualities.

The interest and favorable attitude towards them from readers and critics, the success of books in which such people are portrayed, stimulates writers to "repetition" or "variations" of a certain literary type [2, P. 180].

Quite often, a new literary type arouses the interest of critics, who give it a name (“noble robber”, “superfluous person”, “little person”, “humiliated and insulted”, “nihilist”, “tramp”). The theoretical understanding of literary types is completed by literary critics, based on a wider range of facts in the history of literature [2, P. 238].

The simplest element of characterization is already calling the hero by his own name. In elementary fable forms, sometimes it is enough to simply assign a name to the hero, without any other characteristic (“abstract hero”), in order to fix for him the actions necessary for fabular development. In more complex constructions, it is required that the actions of the hero follow from some psychological unity, so that they are psychologically probable for this character (psychological motivation of actions). In this case, the hero is awarded certain psychological traits.

The characteristic of the hero can be direct, that is, his character is reported directly or from the author, or in the speeches of other characters, or in the self-characterization ("confessions") of the hero. Often there is an indirect characteristic: the character emerges from the actions and behavior of the hero. Sometimes these

actions at the beginning of the narrative are given not in a plot connection, but solely for the purpose of characterization, and therefore these actions not connected with the plot are, as it were, part of the exposition.

In the methods of characterization of characters, two main cases should be distinguished: the character is unchanged, remaining the same in the narrative throughout the plot, and the character is changing, when, as the plot develops, we follow the change in the very character of the character. In the latter case, the elements of characterization enter closely into the plot, and the very change of character (the typical "repentance of the villain") is already a change in the plot situation.

On the other hand, the vocabulary of the hero, the style of his speeches, the topics he touches upon in conversation, can also serve as a hero's mask. But it is not enough to differentiate the heroes, to distinguish them from the general mass of characters by some specific character traits - it is necessary to fix the reader's attention, to arouse this attention and interest in the fate of individual characters. In this regard, the main means is to arouse sympathy for the depicted. Characters are usually emotionally charged. In the most primitive forms, we meet the virtuous and the villainous. Here, the emotional attitude towards the hero (sympathy or repulsion) is developed on a moral basis. Positive and negative "types" are a necessary element of plot construction.

The attraction of the reader's sympathies to the side of some and the repulsive characterization of others cause the reader's emotional participation ("experience") in the events described, his personal interest in the fate of the characters.

It should not be forgotten that the emotional attitude towards the hero is given in the work. The author can attract sympathy for the hero, whose character in everyday life could cause repulsion and disgust in the reader. The emotional attitude towards the hero is a fact of the artistic construction of the work, and only in primitive forms necessarily coincides with the traditional code of morality and community life. The hero is not at all a necessary part of the plot.

The plot as a system of motives can do without a hero and his characteristics. The hero appears as a result of the plot design of the material and is, on the one hand, a means of stringing motives, on the other hand, as if embodied and personified motivation for the connection of motives. This is clear in the elementary narrative form - in the anecdote [3, P. 131-133].

The usual method of grouping and stringing motives is to bring out characters, living carriers of certain motives. The belonging of this or that motive to a certain character facilitates the reader's attention.

The character is a guiding thread that makes it possible to understand the heap of motives, an auxiliary means for classifying and ordering individual motives. On the other hand, there are techniques that help to understand the very mass of characters and their relationships. The character must be able to recognize, on the other hand, it must attract attention to a greater or lesser extent.

The lyrical hero is the image of the poet, the lyrical "I". The inner world of the lyrical hero is revealed not through actions and events, but through a specific state of mind, through the experience of a certain life situation.

A lyrical poem is a concrete and single manifestation of the character of a lyrical hero. With the greatest completeness, the image of the lyrical hero is revealed in all the work of the poet. So, in separate lyrical works of Pushkin ("In the depths of Siberian ores ...", "Anchar", "Prophet", "Desire of glory", "I love you ..." and others), various states of the lyrical hero are expressed, but, taken together, they give us a fairly holistic view of it [3, P.187].

Thus, in the theory of literature, the presence of a person is carried out in such forms as a narrator, a lyrical hero and a character capable of revealing a person with the utmost fullness and breadth. The character who receives the most acute and vivid emotional coloring is called a hero. The hero is the person who is followed by the reader with the greatest tension and attention. The hero evokes compassion, sympathy, joy and grief for the reader.

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